

NOVITAS-ROYAL
RESEARCH ON YOUTH AND LANGUAGE

Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)

ISSN: 1307-4733

OCTOBER 2024

VOLUME: 18

ISSUE: 1

CONTENTS

Internationalization of a Regional Children's Song for Teaching English to Young Learners

Gökçe Nur TÜRKMEN & Kürşat CESUR | pp. 1–17

Reaping the Fruits of Technology-Integrated Grammar Instruction in EFL Classes at the Tertiary Level Through Web 2.0 Tools

Bunyamin CELIK & Saban KARA | pp. 18–36

Systematization of the Teaching of the Turkic Languages in Higher Education

Arailym SARBALINA, Zharkynbike SULEIMENOVA, Kunipa ASHINOVA, Zhaidarkul BELASSAROVA, Balkiya KASSYM & Aiman KOBLANOVA | pp. 37–47

Pre-service EFL Teachers' Online Language Teaching and Their TPACK Development

Behice Ceyda CENGİZ & Işıl Günseli KAÇAR | pp. 48–67

The Axiology of Related Emotions in the Phraseological Units of the Tatar Language

Damir HUSNUTDINOV, Firuza SIBGAEVA, Ruzilya SALAKHOVA, Ramil MIRZAGITOV & Ramilya SAGDIEVA | pp. 68–77

Using Themes and Topics in Contemporary Kazakh Short Fiction: Pedagogical Implications

Orken IMANGALI, Rakymberdi ZHETIBAY, Serik ASSYLBEKULY & Anar KASSYMBEKOVA | pp. 78–87

Wolf Imagery in London's White Fang and Aitmatov's Plakha

Kuttybayev SHOKANKHAN, Kassym BALKIYA, Issayeva Zhazira ISAYEVNA, Koblanova AIMAN & Moldagali BAKYTGUL | pp. 88–98

A Suggested Training Module for Professional Foreign Language Competence

Valentina PANFILOVA, Aleksey PANFILOV, Irina SHESTITKO &
Marina SIRAEVA | pp. 99–111

**Facilitating the Formation of Foreign Language Professionally-oriented
Competence through Problem-based Learning Technology of Non-
linguistic Specialty Students**

Mukasheva Bayan MURATBEKOVNA, Aydan IRGATOGLU, Golovchun Alevtina
ANATOLIEVNA & Karbozova Gulnara KUMISBEKOVNA | pp. 112–128

Metaphors in Media Discourse: A Closer Look at Newspapers

Ludmila BATURINA, Elena PANOVA, Elena TJUMENTSEVA, Zulkhumar
JUMANOVA, Nikolay LEPIKHOV, Ilona KOROLEVA, Galina VOROBEVA
& Elena KHRIPUNOVA | pp. 129–136

**Blended Learning: The Effect on Students' Self-regulation and Academic
Achievements**

Viktor SHURYGIN, Ilyos ABDULLAYEV, Hafis HAJIYEV, Marina
YAKUTINA, Artemiy KOZACHEK & Rafina ZAKIEVA | pp. 137–154

**Professional Training of Future Primary School Teachers Based on
Kazakh National Identity**

Serikkhan ZHUZEYEV¹, Manat ZHAILAUOVA², Aizhan Prmaganbetovna
MAKASHEVA³, Mariyash Shirdayevna JUMAGULOVA⁴ Orazkhan
AIDAROV⁵, Anar KASSYMBEKOVA⁶ | pp. 155–168

**Stylistic Characteristics of Phraseological Units with a Numeric
Component**

Almagul SHINTEMIROVA, Samal SERIKOVA, Ainur YESSETOVA, Akerke
IRGEBAYEVA, Nazgul MINAEVA | pp. 169–178

**Providing an Inclusive Career Guidance for Students with Special
Educational Needs in Kazakhstani Schools**

Laura A. BUTABAYEVA, Svetlana K. ISMAGULOVA, Gulbarshin A.
NOGAIBAYEVA, Umirbekova Akerke NURLANBEKOVNA
& Aidana K. ZHUSSIP | pp. 179–189

**Language Instruction in Kazakhstan's Higher Education: A Critical
Examination**

Tynyshtyk Nurdauletovna YERMEKOVA, Didar RYSKULBEK, Gaini AZIMOVA,
Bizhomart KAPALBEK & Talant MAWKANULI | pp. 190–198